

basified with 40% NaOH solution, and the solid filtered. In some cases extraction with ether and distillation of the thiazole derivative under reduced pressure were necessary. On passing dry HCl gas into an ethereal solution of the thiazoles, hydrochlorides of the respective amino bodies were obtained. 2-Aminothiazole hydrochloride, m.p. 81-82°, as well as 5-methyl-2-aminothiazole hydrochloride, m.p. 94-95°, was analysed correctly for their nitrogen percentage; but 5-ethyl-2-aminothiazole hydrochloride being hygroscopic was analysed as its acetate, m.p. 147° and found in order. Their biguanides were prepared by heating the substituted aminothiazole hydrochloride (1*M*) and dicyandiamide (1*M*) in an oil bath at 145° for 4 hr. with stirring. Isopropanol (100 ml) was then added to the reaction mixture which was refluxed and then filtered. The residue in each case was crystallised from anhydrous ethanol-ether mixture when the thiazolybiguanide hydrochloride (II) separated in brown needles. Particulars of the compounds prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
N¹-(5-Alkyl-2-thiazolyl)biguanide hydrochloride (II).

Compound.	R.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	H	238-40°	27.0	C ₅ H ₆ N ₆ S, HCl	16.40	16.09	37.80	38.10
2	Me	125-26°(d)	17.1	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ S, HCl	15.20	15.15	35.98	35.82
3	Et	218-20°(d)	10.1	C ₇ H ₁₂ N ₆ S, HCl	14.30	14.28	33.80	33.80

N.B.—(d) denotes decomposition.

The Pharmacological screening report of the compounds will be published elsewhere.